

Reactivity of the Methylene Group in Coumarin-4-acetic Acids. Part III. Condensation of 7-Methylcoumarin-4-acetic Acid with *m*- and *p*-Hydroxybenzaldehydes.

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It has been shown (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 107) that salicylaldehyde reacts with coumarin-4-acetic acids, and particularly readily with their ethyl esters, by Knoevenagel's method, forming 4:3'-dicoumaryls. Of other aromatic aldehydes, the condensation of vanillin which has already been reported (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 277) gave a product exhibiting very peculiar colour changes in the presence of alkalis. In view of the remarkable properties possessed by this body, a closer study of its derivatives, and a comparison with compounds of analogous constitution derived from other hydroxyaldehydes seemed to be desirable so as to throw further light on the mechanism of these colour changes.

The methyl ether and the acetyl derivative of the condensation product from vanillin have now been prepared and examined in respect of their behaviour with alkalis. The acetyl compound is insoluble in cold potash but slowly dissolves on warming, due to hydrolysis, and the usual colour effects are reproduced. In case of the methyl ether, on the other hand, it is found that although boiling alkalis dissolve it, evidently by the opening of the pyrone ring, the colour phenomena have disappeared completely, thus lending further support to the view already expressed (*loc. cit.*) that the production of the deep red colour and its subsequent fading should be attributed to the formation, initially, of a molecule which is quinonoid in all its tautomeric forms, this being followed by the opening of the pyrone ring and a consequent return to the normal structure.

A study of properties of the compounds derived from *p*- and *m*-hydroxybenzaldehydes, which are described in this communication has also helped in confirming this hypothesis. The product from

p-hydroxybenzaldehyde possesses a close resemblance to the vanillin compound, the colour of the solid (golden yellow) and the changes it undergoes in solution in alkalis being identical in the two cases, while the *m*-hydroxy body is a colourless solid which dissolves in alkalis with only a faint yellow colour. This is in complete agreement with the expectation that an easy change into the quinonoid form would be possible only in the case of a molecule having a free hydroxyl in the *para*- and not in the *meta*-position

Coumarin-3-acetic acids, which have recently been synthesised in this laboratory, are being condensed with aromatic aldehydes, and it is hoped that the results would prove to be of interest in their bearing on this question.

EXPERIMENTAL.

7-Methyl-4-coumaryl-3':4'-dimethoxyphenylethylene,

It was prepared from the vanillin compound (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 282), by methylation with methyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow laminae melting at 188°. It was insoluble in dilute aqueous potash but dissolved slowly on boiling to a clear solution of a faint yellow colour. On acidification the unchanged methyl ether was deposited in the crystalline form.

7-Methyl-4-coumaryl-3'-methoxy-4'-acetoxyphenylethylene.

This was obtained in the usual way from acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine. It was deposited from glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates melting at 172°. When suspended in dilute sodium hydroxide, it remained unchanged for some minutes but slowly, and more rapidly on warming, the solid dissolved and the solution developed the characteristic red colour. Acids precipitated the original compound derived from vanillin, showing that hydrolysis had taken place.

7-Methyl-4-coumaryl-4'-hydroxyphenylethylene.

The condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with 7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetic acid was effected in the same way as with

vanillin, using Knoevenagel's method (*loc. cit.*). The crude product dissolved readily in a small volume of alcohol, and on allowing the solution to stand for a few hours, most of it separated out. It was further purified by solution in warm sodium hydroxide, precipitation with hydrochloric acid, and a final crystallisation from alcohol which yielded golden yellow plates melting at 218°. The colour reactions with aqueous alkalis and with concentrated sulphuric acid were found to be identical with those of the vanillin product. (Found: C, 76.9; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.7; H, 5.0 per cent.).

The *methyl ether* crystallises from alcohol in fine pale yellow needles, melting at 180°. It dissolved only on boiling for some time with aqueous potash, and when the nearly colourless solution was acidified in the cold, the original methyl ether was slowly reprecipitated (m.p. 180°).

The *acetyl derivative* comes down from dilute acetic acid in colourless needles melting at 209° and slowly dissolves on leaving in contact with cold alkalis. Acidification regenerated the hydroxyphenylethylene (m.p. 218°).

7-Methyl-4-coumaryl-3'-hydroxyphenylethylene.

This product was obtained in a low yield by condensing 7-methylcoumarin-4-acetic acid with *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde in the usual manner. It crystallised best from glacial acetic acid in the form of colourless laminae melting at 207°. It dissolved in cold dilute alkalis with only a pale yellow colour which faded slowly on standing and quickly on warming. The original body was immediately reprecipitated from the yellow solution on the addition of acids, whereas with the colourless solution the process was observed to be much slower. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 5.3. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.7; H, 5.0 per cent.),

The *methyl ether* crystallised as colourless needles from alcohol (m.p. 146°).

The *acetyl derivative* came down from glacial acetic acid as colourless plates (m.p. 159°).

Both the methyl ether and the acetyl compound, like the corresponding compounds derived from the 4'-hydroxyphenylethylene, were only slowly affected by aqueous alkali.

